

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“BLISSFUL IMPASSE”

I loved the soul that shimmered deep in you,
The whispered secrets that your eyes held tight,
The way your spirit danced, forever new,
A beacon burning in the darkest night.

I loved everything about you, perhaps too much,
That smile, that laughter, those eyes so bright,
That humor, a sunbeam, warm and such,
How could I not love you, my guiding light?

You were the echo in my silent prayer,
A melody that lingered, soft and low,
A masterpiece beyond compare,
A gentle current in my steady flow.

You were everything I'd ever wanted, true,
A dream fulfilled, a wish come to pass,
My heart surrendered, completely to you,
Lost in your love, a blissful, sweet impasse.

But love, like starlight, fades with morning's grace,
And dreams dissolve as dawn begins to break,
I release you now, to time and space,
A silent promise for goodness sake.